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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To facilitate the development of the wave energy converter (WEC) industry, a considerable effort needs to be conducted to establish appropriate international guidelines that can reduce uncertainties, standardise e.g. design or manufacturing approaches and streamline the accreditation process up to commercial arrays.

The marine energy industry is still at its infancy, and no dedicated standards have been developed to date. Recently, a number of high-level documents that have approached WEC design and certification have been developed, in particular technical specifications e.g. from the IEC TC114 group. Moreover, more mature industries such as the maritime, oil and gas and offshore wind sectors present similarities to some aspects of the marine renewable energy sector, in aspects such as e.g. structural design of marine structures. A range of key documentation from such industries has been used to date to support the development of WEC devices.

As part of the MegaRoller project, one of the key objectives is to monitor the development of technical specifications, guidelines and standards relevant to the WEC industry, and in particular to the MegaRoller technology. Such monitoring aims to guide the design, implementation and integration of the Power Take-Off (PTO), facilitating its commercialisation. In a preliminary step, a review of the existing standards and their applicability was documented in [D6.6, 2019]. In this document, the final key findings regarding the applicability of technical specifications, guidelines and standards to the MegaRoller technology and to the WEC industry are documented, in an extension of [D6.6, 2019], providing a view of the most up-to-date status of the standardisation work, along with clear recommendations for future activities.

In the next steps, it is recommended that the dissemination activities conducted throughout the MegaRoller project are used to support the future development of standards. In particular, the dissemination of the key test data produced throughout the project, and their associated analysis and findings, aim to contribute to informing the standard requirements. This is particularly valuable, as it is generally recognised that the lack of measured data from testing of WEC devices has hindered progress on the development of standards. The MegaRoller dissemination activities, by taking advantage of analysing and disseminating test data, is anticipated to contribute significantly to such developments, especially as it is focusing on a second-generation WEC, that brings unique insights on the standard requirements.

To incorporate the knowledge collected during the project into technical specifications and, eventually, standards, the relevant technical committees should be engaged with. In particular for the IEC standards, the TC114 committee review and update the standards through maintenance teams typically comprised of National Committee members, with revisions at intervals typically a few years, considering the low maturity of the industry. For the IEC 62600 series, the Stability Date (date at which standards are due for review) ranges from end 2021 (e.g. for IEC TS 62600-100:2012) to 2024 (e.g. for IEC TS 62600-2:2019). It is within these windows that engagement with National Committees on the gaps can be undertaken, through direct participation, engagement with National Committee members, presentation of results at conferences, and publication of academic articles.

It is anticipated that the gaps presented in this deliverable are considered in the next update of the existing marine energy standards.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope of the Document

To facilitate the development of the wave energy converter (WEC) industry, a considerable effort needs to be conducted to establish appropriate international guidelines that can reduce uncertainties, standardise e.g. design or manufacturing approaches and streamline the accreditation process up to commercial arrays.

The marine energy industry is still at its infancy, and no dedicated standards have been developed to date. Recently, a number of high-level documents that have approached WEC design and certification have been developed, in particular technical specifications (TS) e.g. from the International electrotechnical commission (IEC) TC114 group. Moreover, more mature industries such as the maritime, oil and gas and offshore wind sectors present similarities to some aspects of the marine renewable energy sector, in aspects such as e.g. structural design of marine structures. A range of key documentation from such industries has been used to date to support the development of WEC devices.

As part of the MegaRoller project, one of the key objectives is to monitor the development of technical specifications, guidelines and standards relevant to the WEC industry, and in particular to the MegaRoller technology. Such monitoring aims to guide the design, implementation and integration of the Power Take-Off (PTO), facilitating its commercialisation. In a preliminary step, a review of the existing standards and their applicability was documented in [D6.6, 2019]. The report was concluded with a gap analysis related aiming at identifying any salient gaps, and at ensuring the appropriate applicability of relevant design codes during the project.

In this document, the final key findings regarding the applicability of technical specifications, guidelines and standards to the MegaRoller technology and to the WEC industry are documented, in an extension of [D6.6, 2019], providing a view of the most up-to-date status of the standardisation work, along with clear recommendations for future activities.

This report is organised in five (5) main sections. Following this introduction (Section 1), the context of the standardisation activities conducted throughout the MegaRoller project are summarised in Section 2. A high-level gap analysis is then documented in Section 3, guided by the initial analysis conducted at the project's inception, and complemented with more recent inputs. Recommendations for mitigation measures to bridge the identified gaps in the key aspects relevant to the project are then proposed in Section 4. Finally, the report concludes in Section 5 with a summary of the key findings and suggestions for next steps.

1.2 Acceptance Criteria

This document adheres to the description of the deliverable provided in the Grant Agreement [GA, 2018]:

- *“D6.13 is an extension of the standards gap analysis [D6.6, and...] gives the status of the standardisation work and clear recommendations for the future activities.”*

1.3 Abbreviations

API	American petroleum institute
ASME	American society of mechanical engineers
BS	British standard
DNV	Det Norske Veritas AS
EMEC	European marine energy centre
FEM	Finite element method
IEA-OES	International energy agency - Ocean energy system
IEC	International electrotechnical commission
IEEE	Institute of electrical and electronics engineers
ISO	International organization for standardization
ITU	International telecommunication union
LRFD	Load and resistance factor design
O&M	Operation and maintenance
OSS	Offshore service specification
PTO	Power take-off
TRL	Technology readiness level
TS	Technical specification
WEC	Wave energy converter

2 CONTEXT OF THE STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES

2.1 Wave Energy Specificities

The marine energy industry is still in its early days and well-established standards still are lacking worldwide recognition and considerable effort being applied to develop appropriate international standards. The IEC TC114 group has established a number of working groups on specific aspects of the different technologies in an effort to develop technical specifications that can be used to standardise approaches.

Technical specifications, guidelines and standards are essential to support the development of a specific industry. Standards (and codes, when adopted by governmental bodies) constitute a globally accepted set of technical definitions and instructions published by a recognised body. Technical specifications, on the other hand, constitute recommended requirements or guidelines on e.g. materials, components or services. Typically, technical specifications can be transformed into international standards when the technology is mature enough and an international consensus can be reached.

At present, there are no specific standards dedicated to the WEC industry, covering e.g. the design, manufacturing, commissioning and / or operation and maintenance (O&M) stages. Multiple high-level documents that have approached WEC design and certification have already been developed, including:

- i. Det Norske Veritas AS (DNV) Offshore Service Specification (OSS) 312 (DNV-OSS-312, October 2008). Provides an overview the principles and procedures associated with the certification of WECs. It does not include technical provisions [DNV GL, 2008].
- ii. DNV's '*Guidelines on Design and Operation of Wave Energy Converters*', May 2005, The Carbon Trust. This document compiles a list of related standards and outlines methodologies for fatigue analysis (Appendix A) and wave load modelling (Appendix B). [DNV, 2005].
- iii. The European Marine Energy Centre (EMEC) '*Guidelines for Design Basis of Marine Energy Conversion Systems*', 2009. Provides an overview of general aspects behind design basis documentation, covering both wave and tidal energy converters. [EMEC, 2009].
- iv. The IEC TC114 group has issued a number of technical specifications that can be used to standardise the WEC design approach, such as:
 - o IEC TS 62600-100:2012 - Electricity producing wave energy converters - *Power performance assessment* [IEC TS 62600-100:2012].
 - o IEC/TS 62600-2 - Electricity producing wave energy converters - *Design requirements for marine energy systems* [IEC TS 62600-2:2019].
 - o IEC/TS 62600-30 - Electrical power quality requirements for wave, tidal and other water current energy converters.

Furthermore, key documentation from the maritime, oil & gas and offshore wind sectors may be potentially relevant to WEC design, primarily due to the extent of the similarities in the structural design of these structures. However, there is still a significant lack of design consensus in the wave energy sector, with many radically differing device topologies being considered to harness power from the waves. This diversity of concepts complicates the process of producing development and testing guidance.

2.2 MegaRoller Context

The MegaRoller project focused on the design, implementation and integration of a second-generation type wave energy device. The dissemination of key findings, lessons learned, and, critically, real data from testing, brings unique insights on standard requirements, especially considering the generally recognized lack of knowledge transfer and data in the industry to support the development of such standards.

Throughout the project, standardization included the monitoring the progress of the standards related to marine energy and the development of the PTO according to these standards. The objective was to ensure that the deliverables (modular power unit, wave by wave prediction, numerical simulation methodologies etc.) can be used widely throughout the industry, and that the existing codes and standards utilised during the project are fit for purpose.

Standardization input was also obtained from other wave energy industry stakeholders, through general knowledge sharing with the consortium members, and from experience gained in other industries, through literature review.

Such knowledge and input culminated in the conduction of a gap analysis, in particular in the guidance for testing WEC PTO systems, but also more general topics. It is anticipated that the dissemination of these lessons learned and gap analysis to relevant standardization bodies, such as the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), International organization for standardization (ISO), etc. can provide valuable input for the definition of the next iteration of standards.

2.3 COVID Context

It is noted that, due to the COVID pandemic, the standardization activities conducted were limited to lessons learnt exchanges with the MegaRoller partners, as presential workshops during which specific topics could have been discussed were significantly restricted.

3 GAP ANALYSIS

A gap analysis was undertaken as part of the MegaRoller project in [D6.6, 2019] to identify areas that are not well covered by existing documents. This deliverable provides an update to that gap analysis, building on the knowledge of the partners.

3.1 Findings from gap analysis

At a high-level, a WEC system can be broken down into the following key subsystems [SDWED, 2014] – see also Figure 3-1:

- A hydrodynamic subsystem, that captures the wave power in an efficient manner.
- A reaction subsystem, that maintains the position of the WEC and transfers the loads to the seabed.
- A PTO subsystem, that converts the captured wave power into grid-quality electric power.
- A control subsystem and instrumentation, that measures target variables and controls the device.
- An electrical generation and power transmission subsystem, that transfers the electrical power.
- An interface subsystem, where the different WEC subsystem blocks interact with the others.

Figure 3-1 Typical WEC block diagram with key subsystems [SDWED, 2014]

The review of the existing codes and standards relevant to the WEC industry conducted in [D6.6, 2019] evidenced two essential differences between WECs and other, more mature offshore applications:

1. Being (in general) unmanned structures, the safety factors of WECs associated with a specific failure could potentially be lower than the ones currently recommended in the standards, as the consequence of failure may be reduced when compared to equivalent failure in a manned structure.
2. WEC subsystems may be subject to different loads, which may require consideration of specific dominant failure modes. For example, design for near resonance can lead to fatigue becoming a governing failure mechanism, which in turn affects WEC reliability.

Table 3-1 summarises the main gaps identified in [D6.6, 2019] that should be bridged to support the standardisation of the WEC industry. The matrix is organised by subsystems, following the approach proposed in e.g. [SDWED, 2014]. A colour code is used to prioritise the standardisation effort required:

Low priority No gaps or few gaps identified, requiring only minor updates to the relevant standard(s).	Medium priority Significant gap(s) identified, requiring some revision of the relevant standard(s).	High priority Major gap(s) identified, requiring a significant revision of the relevant standard(s), or a new standard.

Table 3-1: Identified gaps in the existing standards: Priority levels for developments [D6.6, 2019].

Subsystem(s)	Topic(s) covered	Identified gap(s)	Priority level
Hydrodynamic	Structural design. Fatigue assessment. Reliability assessment. Manufacturing and testing.	The interaction with the PTO system is typically not considered. The safety factors may be too conservative.	
Reaction	Design approaches. Manufacturing and testing. Design and construction.	The interaction with the PTO system is typically not considered. The safety factors may be too conservative.	
PTO	All off-the-shelf components. Strength analysis. Design, construction, inspection, testing. Manufacturing and testing. Machinery safety.	The interaction with advanced control strategy may need to be further considered. The mechanical loading and maintenance regime may be outside of the standard specifications.	
Instrumentation and control	Functional and electromagnetic compatibility. Operating conditions, electrical interfaces, performance requirements and data transmission protocols. Safety requirements. Design and integration.	Operational safety, requirements for control systems.	
Electrical generation and power transmission	Design. Operation. Power quality. Grid code compliance.	Existing standards designed for manned offshore structures.	
Interface	Protective coating. Sealings.	The mechanical loading may be outside of the standard specifications (e.g. for sealings). Subsea electrical connectors are not covered.	
Other aspects	Health and safety. Marine operations (except decommissioning).	Decommissioning of gravity-based structures are not covered. Some standardisation of the EIA processes involved would be beneficial.	

3.2 Updated Input

3.2.1 Findings from MegaRoller Implementation

Although scaled testing is a well-established practice, the challenges and specificities brought by the wave energy sector mean that a significant effort need to be put in developing testing guidelines and standards to support the research phase, and the development of the sector into an industry.

The dominant loading(s) specific to the system need to be identified and scaled properly, and the complex marine conditions need to be representative for the results to be meaningful.

In general, the MegaRoller test bench and PTO design is based on commonly used engineering principles. Therefore, most of the existing standards could relatively be easily followed during the development of the project. Table 3-2 presents the list of key standards and directives that were referred to throughout the Project [AWE, 2021].

One general gap, identified in [D6.6, 2019] and confirmed during the development of the project, relates to all strength and fatigue analysing standards: It needs to be considered whether current standards provide too conservative results when analysing the steel structures. There may be a need for additional testing of the materials used in the PTO for knowing more accurate fatigue loading properties of the material. The existing strength and fatigue analysing standards have not been developed for analysing steel structures in such conditions where the panel is constantly moving back and forth.

Table 3-2 List of key standards specifically used in the MegaRoller project [AWE, 2021]

Type	Name/Description	Number/ID	Used in
Directive	Electromagnetic compatibility directive	2004/108/EC	All
Directive	Directive 2006/42/EC on machinery	2006/42/EC	All
Directive	Low voltage directive	2006/95/EC	All
Directive	Pressure equipment directive (PED)	97/23/EC	All
Standards for offshore steel structures:			
Standard	Fatigue design of offshore steel structures	DNVGL-RP-C203	Design of steel structures
Standard	Design of offshore steel structures, general (LRFD method)	DNVGL-OS-C101	Design of steel structures
Standard	Fabrication and testing of offshore structures	DNVGL-OS-C401	Design of steel structures
Standard	Design of Offshore Wind Turbine Structures	DNVGL-OS-J101	Design of steel structures
Standard	Marine and machinery systems and equipment	DNVGL-OS-D101	Used as reference
Standard	Electrical installations	DNVGL-OS-D201	Used as reference
Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC and pressure equipment directive:			
Standard	Safety of machinery. Risk assessment. Part 1: Principles.	SFS-EN ISO 14121-1	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery. Risk assessment. Part 2: Practical guidance and examples of methods.	SFS-EN ISO 14121-2	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery; General principles for design – Risk assessment and risk reduction	EN ISO 12100:2010	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery – Electrical equipment of machines – Part 1: General requirements	EN 60204-1:2006	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Hydraulic fluid power – General rules and safety requirements for system and their components	EN ISO 4413:2010	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Pressure equipment. Part 7: Safety systems for unfired pressure equipment	EN 764-7:2002	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery – Safety-related parts of control system – Part 1: General principles	EN ISO 13849-1:2008	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery – Safety-related parts of control system – Part 2: Validation	EN ISO 13849-2:2012	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery; Guards – General requirements for the design and constructions	EN 953:1997 + A1:2009	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery – Interlocking devices associated with guards – Principles for design	EN 1088:1995 + A2:2008	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery – Emergency stop – Principles for design	EN ISO 13850:2008	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery – Prevention of unexpected start-up	EN 1037:1995 + A1:2008	Test bench and PTO

Standard	Safety of machinery – Ergonomic design principles – Part 1	EN 614-1:2006 + A1:2009	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery. Indication, marking and actuation	EN 61310-1:2008	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety of machinery - Permanent means of access to machinery - Part 1: Choice of fixed means and general requirements of access	EN ISO 14122-1-4:2016	Test bench and PTO
Low Voltage Directive 2006/95/EC, electromagnetic compatibility directive and other electrical installations:			
Standard	Low voltage electrical installations (European version: HD 60364 Low voltage electric installations)	SFS6000	Test bench and PTO
Standard	High voltage electrical installations (European versions: EN 61936-1)	SFS6001	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Safety in electrical work (European version: EN 50110-1:2013)	SFS6002	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Low voltage switchgear and control gear assemblies - Part 1: General rules	EN 61439-1:2013	Test bench and PTO
Standard	Marine energy - Wave, tidal and other water current converters - Part 100: Electricity producing wave energy converters - Power performance assessment	IEC TS 62600-100:2012	PTO validation
Standard	Marine energy – Wave, tidal and other water current converters – Part 30: Electrical power quality requirements	IEC TS 62600-30:2018	PTO validation
Standard	Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 4-7: Testing and measurement techniques	IEC 6100-4-7	PTO validation
Standard	Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 4-15: Testing and measurement techniques – Flickermeter – Functional and design specifications	IEC 61000-4-15	PTO validation
Standard	Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) – Part 4-30: Testing and measurement techniques - Power quality measurement methods	IEC 61000-4-30	PTO validation
Standard	Power quality measurement in power supply systems – Part 1: Power quality instruments (PQI)	IEC 62586-1	PTO validation
Standard	Power quality measurement in power supply systems – Part 2: Functional tests and uncertainty requirements	IEC 62586-2	PTO validation

3.2.2 Updates from New Literature

Since the issue of the initial gap analysis [D6.6, 2019], the IEC Technical Committee TC114 has published four (4) relevant parts of TS 62600 Marine energy—wave, tidal and other water current converters—as summarised below.

- Part 1:2020 Vocabulary [IEC TS 62600-1:2020] gives an updated terminology for the series.
- Part 2:2019 Marine energy systems—design requirements [IEC TS 62600-2:2019] has also been updated with design conditions unique to marine energy converters.
- Part 3:2019 Measurement of mechanical loads [IEC TS 62600-3:2020] covers this for the purpose of load simulation, model validation, and certification. It also includes guidance on full-scale testing.
- Part 4:2020 Specification for establishing the qualification of new technology [IEC TS 62600-4:2020] has updated the qualification of development.

The Ocean Energy System from the International Energy Agency (IEA-OES) recently published a detailed evaluation and guidance framework for ocean energy technologies, resulting from the ‘Task 12’ activities [IEA-OES, 2021]. This captures six (6) technology development stages, from concept creation to commercial scale array demonstration, and nine (9) evaluation areas (e.g. reliability, survivability etc.) with corresponding evaluation criteria and recommended activities to complete in each stage of development. Such guidance is particularly important to structure the development plan of marine energy technologies, describing an incremental staged approach from concept to commercialisation, with increasing complexity and costs, with clear evaluation criteria (metrics/key performance indicators) at each stage.

In parallel to the continuous development of guidelines and standards, standardisation activities were also conducted under a range of projects, also looking at bridging the gaps between the existing standards and the wave energy sector’s requirements. For example, WP5 of the OPERA project was dedicated to providing the first documented application of the marine energy related IEC TS, reduce the uncertainties in their application and provide recommendations to the IEC TC114 committee. Deliverable D5.2 documented the exercise, containing a description of the work carried out, results and uncertainties in relation to wave measurement, WEC power and WEC power performance assessment, electrical power quality and assessment of mooring systems. Besides the experience gained within the project and challenges associated with the experimental work and with the application of the TS were also reported. Finally, the report provides recommendations for possible improvements on each TS.

Similarly, the MaRINET2 project focused on reviewing and providing feedback on guidelines for testing ORE devices. Given the project’s setup, perspectives from both the laboratory personnel undertaking the testing and technology developers were considered in [MaRINET2, D2.26] and [MaRINET2, D2.7], respectively, presenting feedback from both groups.

Additionally, a standardised test verification process was outlined in [MaRINET2, D2.4], allowing third parties to independently verify that tests conducted have been carried out in a scientific and logical way, to ensure robustness of the results. In particular, [MaRINET2, D4.4], covering electrical subsystems and grid integration, proposed approaches to testing the grid connection of marine renewable technologies, both at present and in the future.

4 STANDARDISATION RECOMMENDATIONS

This section presents the gaps that have been identified in the guidance for testing WEC devices, based on literature review and experience throughout the MegaRoller project. For each gap identified, a short description of the gap and why it is important is presented, together with reference to the guidance that does exist.

4.1 Development Pathway

Clear and specific industry standards and development pathways are necessary to ensure efficient testing processes along which the technology developers can progress, until commercialisation. At present, only limited approaches, still quite broad due to the diversity in wave energy technologies, are available to the sector, and some key areas where recommendations are needed remain insufficiently addressed.

The current, most accepted and used, staged development approach of WEC technologies is based on the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) assessment. The concept of TRL for MRE technologies has been described and developed in the Australian Renewable Energy Agency (ARENA). Each stage is structured following a set of requirements that the concept/prototype needs to meet in order to validate the development stage. In general, a testing campaign aims at validation of a specific TRL level to reach the next one and prove reliability of the device. More recently, a comprehensive development progression framework is described in the IEC TS on early-stage testing of WECs [IEC TS 62600-103:2020], and the IEA 'Task 12' group has developed a standardised set of metrics to quantify technology development [IEA-OES, 2021] (see also Section 2). The technology development is organised in six (6) technology development stages, from concept creation to commercial scale array demonstration, and nine (9) evaluation areas (e.g. reliability, survivability etc.) with corresponding evaluation criteria and recommended activities to complete in each stage of development.

However, general feedback from the project is that the development progression frameworks described are still lacking the definition of threshold for the metrics considered. It is understood that such gap is mostly due to the diversity of the sector, where vastly differing concepts and scales are being developed, and successful development could be reached despite very different combinations of evaluation criteria, for different markets, investors etc. Nonetheless, the definition of such thresholds would facilitate the tracking of progresses for developers, as an indication of the whether they are on the correct pathway to a successful commercial product.

In general, areas where further guidance would be needed include how to scale up tests from controlled to uncontrolled environments and, similarly, progression from the laboratory to the sea. More detail is perhaps needed on what should be tested at each stage of development, and facilities for doing so. Similarly, what is required to progress from one stage-gate to the next may need more detail.

4.2 PTO Subsystem and Interaction with Other Subsystems

As the MegaRoller project focused on the development of a PTO, this standardisation activities mainly highlighted the gaps existing in the guidelines and standards related to this subsystem. Moreover, it can be seen in Section 2 that the most critical gaps identified were essentially related to the lack of consideration brought in the interaction between the PTO system and the other subsystems (in particular hydrodynamic and reaction subsystems).

The PTO converts the captured wave power into grid-quality electric power by transferring the motions and forces of the hydrodynamic subsystem to the generator shaft [SDWED, 2014]. The MegaRoller PTO can be categorised as a hydraulic system, where the cyclic motion of the hydrodynamic subsystem causes the linear actuator (i.e. the hydraulic cylinder) to move back and forth. The reciprocating motion of the actuator pumps the fluid through the hydraulic system, and a specific arrangement of valves and accumulators controls and diverts the fluid to the hydraulic motor. The hydraulic motor then rotates the generator shaft.

A hydraulic system typically consists of the following key components:

- Valves, that control the flow, pressure and direction.
- Motors, that convert the fluid power to linear or rotary mechanical motion.
- Pumps and cylinders, that convert the rotary or linear mechanical power to fluid power.
- Fluid conditioning, that condition the fluid characteristics (e.g. filters, heaters...).
- Fluid connectors, that connect the different fluid components (e.g. pipe, manifold...).
- Accumulators, that store the potential fluid power.
- Hydraulic fluid, that can be water-based or oil-based.

The operation of the PTO also depends on a number of auxiliary subsystems (e.g. brake / latch system, shock absorption system, heating / cooling system etc.), that aim to maintain the operational conditions for safe and reliable operation of the PTO.

In order to enhance the reliability, improve the ease of maintenance, increase the availability of spare parts, and reduce the costs of the MegaRoller system, the PTO is being designed using as much as possible off-the-shelf, standard components such as generators, hydraulic motors or hydraulic accumulators. The design and manufacturing of these components is extensively supported by recognised industry standards. Table 4-1 provides a shortlist of key documentation that are potentially relevant to the structural design of PTO subsystems, focusing on the assembly rather than on the component level.

Overall, the PTO subsystem is relatively well covered at component-level by recognised, international standards. Although a hydraulic PTO technology is relatively standard, its specific application to WEC systems may involve a range of potentially new aspects, related e.g.:

- The interaction with a complex control subsystem.
- The characteristics of the mechanical loading on the hydraulic actuators.
- The characteristics of the electrical loading on the high-power drive for controlling the generators.
- The fatigue life of the dynamic seals, in face of the loading conditions.
- The maintenance regime.

It should be noted that, with regard to the specific case of the MegaRoller hydraulic PTO subsystem, the novelty aspect in the above listed points remains fairly limited, in particular when considering that the control system is limited to a damping control strategy, and that hydraulic accumulators limit the fluctuation in the generator speed. Therefore, no specific gaps have yet been identified; however, such assessment may evolve as the MegaRoller PTO design progresses from a concept phase to a more detailed design stage.

Table 4-1 Core documentation: PTO subsystem

Doc. Reference	Application / Relevance	Supporting / Additional Documents
DNVGL-OS-C101 (2018) Design of offshore steel structures, general – LRFD method.	Strength analysis in finite element method (FEM).	DNVGL-CG-0127 (2015- Amended 2016) Finite element analysis. DNVGL-RP-C203 (2016) Fatigue design of offshore steel structures. DNVGL-OS-D101 (2018) Machine and machinery systems and equipment.
PD 5500:2018+A1:2018 Specification for unfired fusion welded pressure vessels.	Design, construction, inspection and testing of unfired pressure vessels. Pressure containment of the hydraulic cylinders.	BS EN 13445 Unfired pressure vessels. BPVC-VIII-1 (2017) ASME’s Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code Section VII – Rules for Construction of Pressure Vessels Division 1.
DNVGL-OS-C401 (2018 – Amended 2019) Fabrication and testing of offshore structures.	Manufacturing and testing, for example leakage tests.	ISO 4406:2017 Hydraulic fluid power - Fluids - Method for coding the level of contamination by solid particles.
ISO 12100:2010 Safety of machinery; General principles for design – Risk assessment and risk reduction. ISO 4413:2010 Hydraulic fluid power – General rules and safety requirements for system and their components. BS EN 764-7:2002 Pressure equipment. Part 7: Safety systems for unfired pressure equipment.	Machinery safety.	BS EN 60204-1:2018 Safety of machinery – Electrical equipment of machines – Part 1: General requirements. ISO 4126-1:2013 Safety devices for protection against excessive pressure – Part 1: Safety valves.

One of the most prevalent themes for additional standards, also related to the need for development pathways guidance discussed in Section 4.1, was related to the effective scaling and simulation of PTO at model scale, along with methods for performance assessment. In general, for early development stage testing campaigns, there is a lack of standardised guidance on building a mechanism representative of the PTO (power conversion chain similitude) and assessing their performances. More detailed methods for PTO performance assessment would, therefore, be useful for the sector.

Lastly, the testing plan development highlighted the need for more detailed standards describing a process for uncertainty analysis. For example, IEC TS 62600-100 [IEC TS 62600-100:2012] on power performance assessment for WECs refers to wind standards for uncertainty case studies, but no standardised process dedicated to WEC devices has been produced to date, and no clear requirement on how the uncertainty results should be displayed in the outputs are provided. In contrast, the IEC technical specification for wind turbine performance assessment 61400-12-1 [IEC 61400-12-1:2017] provides a proper uncertainty case study. Equivalent case studies applied to WECs, especially for the resource uncertainties, would be helpful and would help to standardise the calculation process, such as conducted e.g. in the MaRINET2 project round robin activities [Judge, 2021] and through the transnational access programme [Robertson, 2018].

4.3 Electrical Generation and Power Transmission

The main function of the power transmission subsystem is to transfer the electrical power in an efficient and reliable manner from the WEC until the grid (or the consumption source) [SDWED, 2014]. Typically, it consists of a high-power electrical equipment such as generators, transformers, switchboards, switchgears, connectors and power cables.

Table 4-2 provides a shortlist of key documentation from these sectors that are potentially relevant to the design of the electrical generation and power transmission subsystems.

Table 4-2 Core documentation: Electrical generation and power transmission subsystems

Doc. Reference	Application / Relevance	Supporting / Additional Documents
IEC 60364 Low voltage electric installations.	Design, erection, and verification of low-voltage electrical installations.	IEC 61439-1:2011 Low voltage switchgear and control gear assemblies - Part 1: General rules.
IEC 61936-1:2010 + AMD1:2014 CSV Power installations exceeding 1kV a.c.	Design and erection of electrical power installations in systems with nominal voltages above 1kV a.c.	BS EN 50522:2010 Earthing of power installations exceeding 1kV a.c.
BS EN 50110-1:2013 Operation of electrical installations – Part 1: General requirements.	Operation of and work activity on, with, or near electrical Installations.	-
DNVGL-RP-0360 (2016) Subsea power cables in shallow water.	Design, manufacturing, installation, operation and maintenance of subsea cables.	ISO 13628-5:2009 Design and operation of subsea production systems - Part 5: Subsea umbilicals. BS EN 62230:2007+A1:2014 Electric cables. Spark-test method. ITU-T G.976 (2014) Test methods applicable to optical fibre submarine cable systems. DNVGL-ST-F201 (2018) Dynamic risers. IEC 60502-1:2004+AMD1:2009 Consolidated version API SPEC 17E (2017) Specifications for subsea umbilicals.
IEC TS 62600-30:2018 Wave, tidal and other water current converters - Part 30: Electrical power quality requirements.	Definition and specification of the quantities to be determined for characterizing the power quality of a marine energy converter unit; measurement procedures for quantifying the characteristics of a marine energy converter.	
DNVGL-ST-0125 (2016) Grid Code compliance.	Framework for proving grid code compliance by means of technical assessment, test, measurement, validation and simulation.	DNVGL-SE-0124 (2016) Certification of grid code compliance.

In general, the connection arrangements involve a number of requirements in accordance with national grid codes that must be adhered to in order to gain permission for connecting the WEC power plant to the local electrical grid. Recommendations provided in [DNVGL-ST-0125](#) specify that the electrical design shall conform with the grid codes specific to the relevant market areas; in the context of the MegaRoller

project, considering the Peniche deployment site, the Portuguese grid code [MEID, 2010] was accounted for. However, there is overall a lack of exclusive standard of test methodologies, and of dedicated grid connection normative. This is in general due to the maturity of the sector, that is at present focusing more on early-stage developments, and where limited projects have looked into grid connection issues.

A comparative analysis of European grid codes relevant to offshore renewable energy installations is provided in [Robles, 2019]. It reviews basic concepts and control requirements for grid integration of marine farms and identifies the key challenges that need to be overcome to enable such grid integration. In general, it is shown that the grid code variability from country to country is likely to represent the main obstacle to smooth grid connection.

The development of grid connection guidelines and standards also need to consider the wave-compatible requirements, to complete those already developed for the wind energy sector. For example, the IEC TS 62600-30 standard [IEC TS 62600-30:2018] provides general rules about the power quality and test procedures for wave, tidal and other water current energy devices, but appears to be lacking clear directions on the compliance of the facility with these quality criteria. Also, some of the codes and standards listed in Table 4-2 were designed for manned offshore installations. Revisions of these may be required to consider the operation of WEC devices under normal conditions, where the WEC is normally unmanned, to adjust items directly related to the safety of operating staff. For example, requirements for internal ambient conditions (e.g. minimal ventilation, removal of waste heat produced) could be reassessed to account for the unmanned conditions of operation.

5 CONCLUSION

One of the key reasons for applying standards is to facilitate the accreditation process of the commercial arrays, ensuring that the deliverables (modular power unit, wave by wave prediction, numerical simulation methodologies etc.) can be used widely throughout the industry. The marine energy industry is still at its infancy, and no dedicated standards have been developed to date. However, a number of high-level documents that have approached WEC design and certification have recently been developed, in particular technical specifications e.g. from the IEC TC114 group. Moreover, more mature industries such as the maritime, oil and gas and offshore wind sectors present similarities to some aspects of the marine renewable energy sector, in aspects such as e.g. structural design of marine structures. A range of key documentation from such industries has been used to date to support the development of WEC devices.

As the wave energy sectors matures and grows, the standards and guidelines need to be improved to reflect the latest best practices and guide the next developments. Throughout the project, the consortium monitored the development of the standards related to marine energy and strived to apply those in the context of the PTO design, implementation and integration. The gap analysis initially conducted in [D6.6, 2019] was then updated, using feedback from the project and considering the latest published literature, with the objective of highlighting some of the key issues that should be addressed to facilitate the design and development of the emerging WEC industry.

This report aims to disseminate lessons learned throughout the project, in particular in an effort to inform the relevant standardization bodies, such as the IEEE, ISO, etc. The gap analysis provided in this report documents the final key findings regarding the applicability of technical specifications, guidelines and standards to the MegaRoller technology and to the WEC industry at the completion of the project, in an extension of [D6.6, 2019], providing a view of the most up-to-date status of the standardisation work. Clear recommendations for future activities are also provided in the next section

The report can be considered a starting point for further standardisation work, highlighting some of the key issues that should be addressed to facilitate the design and development of the emerging WEC industry.

In the next steps, the dissemination activities conducted throughout the MegaRoller project can be used to continue supporting the future development of standards. In particular, the publication of the key test data produced throughout the project, and their associated analysis and findings, should be used to inform the standard requirements. This is particularly valuable, as it is generally recognised that the lack of measured data from testing of WEC devices has hindered progress on the development of standards. The MegaRoller dissemination activities, by taking advantage of analysing and disseminating test data, are anticipated to contribute significantly to such developments, especially as the project focused on a second-generation WEC, bringing unique insights on the standard requirements.

To incorporate the knowledge collected during the project into technical specifications and, eventually, standards, the relevant technical committees should be engaged with. In particular for the IEC standards, the TC114 committee review and update the standards through maintenance teams typically comprised of National Committee members, with revisions at intervals typically a few years, considering the low maturity of the industry. For the IEC 62600 series, the Stability Date (date at which standards are due for review) ranges from end 2021 (e.g. for IEC TS 62600-100:2012) to 2024 (e.g. for IEC TS 62600-2:2019). It is within these windows that engagement with National Committees on the gaps can be undertaken,

through direct participation, engagement with National Committee members, presentation of results at conferences, and publication of academic articles.

It is anticipated that the gaps presented in this deliverable are considered in the next update of the existing marine energy standards.

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